

ARCHER2 Service Description

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11 Dec 2024

EPCC

The University of Edinburgh

1. Abstract

ARCHER2 is the latest iteration of the UK National Supercomputing Service. The ARCHER2 service aims to provide a flexible and responsive resource to support world-class research in the UK; to improve the skill sets of researchers and RSEs to equip them for the future; to improve the sustainability, maintainability of the HPC software base; and to enable collaboration and outreach to the wider, worldwide HPC community and beyond. The service consists of four main components: hardware provided by HPE, Service Provision (SP) support provided by EPCC, Computational Science and Engineering (CSE) support provided by EPCC, and hosting provided by the University of Edinburgh. The hardware from HPE provides the computational resource around which the service is built, it is a HPE Cray EX system with 5,860 compute nodes each with two AMD 7420 64-core processors and 256 GB or 512 GB DDR4 RAM. Compute nodes are connected using a HPE Cray Slingshot 10 interconnect in a dragonfly topology. There are 750,080 CPU cores available to researchers on ARCHER2 along with over 15 PB of storage and an extensive suite of modelling and simulation packages and supporting software. The EPCC SP support provides system administration, user and project management, and service desk management. The EPCC CSE support provides in-depth technical support for users, extensive training, embedded CSE support to fund software development, and outreach to the wider public. Hosting from University of Edinburgh provides the physical infrastructure to host the ARCHER2 system and networking to connect it to the outside world.

2. ARCHER2 objectives

ARCHER2 is primarily a vehicle for delivering high-quality research outputs. As such, all our service activities ultimately support that key objective. We ensure that the activities of all elements of the service support the user community and so contribute to the delivery of world-leading research.

As Service Provider, EPCC coordinates and interfaces with all the elements of the Service to ensure good co-operation and clearly defined responsibilities. All service partners work together to ensure that the ARCHER2 service matches users' evolving needs.

Key characteristics of the ARCHER service are:

- User-focused: The service is user-focused, flexible and responsive to users' continually evolving needs.
- Experienced: The service is delivered by high-quality staff with a wide range of knowledge, experience of national HPC services, and respected standing within the worldwide HPC ecosystem.
- Committed: All service partners have long-standing commitments to providing high-quality national HPC services that facilitate world-leading science.
- Collaborative: The service engages with the whole UK HPC community through an open and inclusive approach to service delivery, supported by our strong existing links into the wider community.
- High quality: The service is underpinned by certified Quality Management processes (ISO9001) and Information Security policies (ISO27001).
- Sustainable: The service is committed to understanding, tracking, and minimising our emissions and environmental impact.
- Approachable, accessible and inclusive: We take a holistic approach to support recognising and respecting the diversity of needs across the community.
- Flexible and adaptable: Drawing on a large pool of experienced staff, the service adapts to changing requirements and technical needs, variable levels of demand, and to external forces.
- Available and timely: The service is staffed by experienced individuals with a large amount of technical knowledge.
- Open and responsive: The service proactively solicits feedback from the user community and acts on it in an appropriate way to continually improve the service.

3. Service partners

ARCHER2 is provided by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) – EPSRC and NERC, EPCC, the University of Edinburgh and HPE.

UKRI is the managing agent for the ARCHER2 service. This is a non-departmental, public body sponsored by the UK Government Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT). UKRI brings together the seven disciplinary research councils, Research England, and the UK's innovation agency, Innovate UK.

EPCC, part of the University of Edinburgh, hosts ARCHER2 and is responsible for the delivery of the Service Provision contract and Computational Science and Engineering contract. EPCC is the UK's leading centre of supercomputing and data science expertise. The centre provides world-class Supercomputing and data facilities and services for science and business. The goal is to accelerate the effective exploitation of novel computing throughout industry, academia, and commerce.

The University of Edinburgh is a world-leading university of academic excellence. Opened in 1583, it is one of the UK's oldest Universities. The University is home to the Advanced Computing Facility (ACF), EPCC's high-performance-computing data centre. The facility hosts a range of HPC and data equipment with associated plant rooms for the power and infrastructure.

The ARCHER2 hardware is provided by a Cray EX supercomputer system that was procured from Cray. In late 2019, Cray was acquired by Hewlett Packard Enterprise (HPE). There are two HPE teams directly involved in supporting the ARCHER2 service. The on-site support team is based at the ACF and manages hardware and system software support on a 7x24 basis, liaising closely with EPCC and the HPE Centre of Excellence team to provide comprehensive support for the user community. The Centre of Excellence (CoE) supports the ARCHER2 service by providing, for example, in-depth support accessed through helpdesk channels, tailored training, and specific community support.

4. User communities and access

The UK computational-science community is a critical element of the ARCHER2 service, as the entity that will realise the potential for scientific exploitation to progress priority UK research areas. Most of the science undertaken on ARCHER2 is from the engineering, physical sciences, and environmental sciences, as represented by the UKRI funding bodies, EPSRC and NERC, that fund the Service. To focus research activities, EPSRC and NERC have created thematic consortia – called High-end Computing Consortia and NERC Consortia, respectively. There are, at the time of writing, eleven consortia (eight from EPSRC and three from NERC) based around UK science priorities¹. The consortia are allocated a large fraction of of the computational time on the ARCHER2 service

Other UK-based researchers have opportunities to use the ARCHER2 service, through various award schemes that run over the lifetime of the service, addressing the full range of computational-readiness, from early access 'pump-priming' through to capability-scale 'pioneer' awards. EPCC is also assigned a small amount of ARCHER2 resources, referred to as Director's Time, to undertake research and development, as well as small-scale computational activities, including international collaboration, in support of the wider ARCHER2 community.

5. Hardware and system software

Overview

The ARCHER2 hardware is a HPE Cray EX supercomputing system which has a total of 5,860 CPU compute nodes. Each compute node has 128 cores (dual AMD EPYC 7742 64-core 2.25 GHz processors)

¹ <https://www.archer2.ac.uk/research/consortia/> (accessed on 10th December 2024).

giving a total of 750,080 cores. There are two test and development GPU compute nodes, each with four AMD MI210 GPU accelerators. Compute nodes are connected by a HPE Slingshot interconnect.

There are also User Access Nodes (UAN, also called login nodes), which provide access to the system; and data-analysis nodes, which are configured to facilitate the preparation of job inputs and analysis of job outputs. The UAN have the same architecture as the high memory compute nodes. More detail on the compute nodes is provided below. Compute nodes are only available to users via the Slurm job scheduling system.

There are several different storage systems available on ARCHER2, including high-performance parallel Lustre file systems, solid-state storage. More details on the available storage systems are provided below.

CPU compute nodes

The CPU compute nodes each have 128 cores. They are dual-socket nodes with two, 64-core, AMD EPYC 7742 processors. There are 5,276 standard-memory nodes and 584 high-memory nodes. Each socket contains eight Core Complex Dies (CCDs) and one I/O die (IOD). Each CCD contains two Core Complexes (CCXs). Each CCX has 4 cores and 16 MB of L3 cache. Table 1 provides details of CPU compute node hardware and Figure 1 shows compute node hardware layout.

GPU compute nodes

The test and development GPU compute nodes each have 32 CPU cores and 4 GPU accelerators. They are single socket nodes with one, 32-core, AMD EPYC 7543P processor. Each node has four AMD Instinct MI210 GPUs. There are 2 GPU nodes. Table 2 provides details of GPU compute node hardware.

Interconnect

ARCHER2 has a HPE Slingshot interconnect with 200 Gb/s signalling per node. It uses a dragonfly topology with the following layout:

- Nodes are organized into groups. Each group has:
 - 128 compute nodes each with two Network Interface Cards (NIC)
 - Each node is connected to two switches via electrical connections from NICs to switches
 - 16 32-port switches per group. Each switch:
 - 8 downlink ports connected to nodes (dragonfly L0, electrical)
 - 15 crosslink ports to other switches in group (dragonfly L1, electrical)
 - 9 uplink ports to other groups (dragonfly L2, optical)
 - All-to-all connection amongst switches in a group using electrical links (dragonfly L1).
- All-to-all connection between groups using optical links (dragonfly L0).
- Two groups per ARCHER2 Cabinet.

Table 1: ARCHER2 CPU compute node hardware details

Component	Details
Processor	2 × AMD Zen2 (Rome) EPYC 7742, 64-core, 2.25 GHz
CPU cores per node	128
NUMA structure	8 NUMA regions per node (16 cores per NUMA region)
Memory per node	256 GB (standard), 512 GB (high memory) DDR4
Memory per core	2 GB (standard), 4 GB (high memory) DDR4
L1 cache	32 kB/core
L2 cache	512 kB/core
L3 cache	16 MB/4-cores
Vector support	AVX2
Network connection	2 × 100 Gb/s injection ports per node

Figure 1: Diagram showing ARCHER2 compute node layout.

Storage

The ARCHER2 service, like many HPC systems, has a complex storage layout. There are several different data storage types available to users:

- Home file systems
- Work file systems
- Solid-state (NVMe) scratch file system
- RDFaaS (RDF as a Service) file systems

Each type of storage has different characteristics and policies and is suitable for different types of use.

The home file system is provided by dual NetApp FAS8200A systems (one primary and one disaster recovery) with a capacity of 1 PB each.

The work file system consists of four separate HPE Cray L300 storage systems, each with a capacity of 3.6 PB. The system also includes 1.1 PB of solid-state, NVMe storage, provided by an HPE Cray E1000 appliance.

Table 2: ARCHER2 GPU compute node hardware details

Component	Details
Processor	1 × AMD EPYC 7543P, 632-core, 2.8 GHz
CPU cores per node	32
GPU accelerator	AMD Instinct MI210 (CDNA2, 104 CU, 64 GB HBM2e)
GPUs per node	4
NUMA structure	4 NUMA regions per node (8 cores per NUMA region)
Memory per node	512 GB DDR4
Memory per core	16 GB
L1 cache	32 kB/core
L2 cache	512 kB/core
L3 cache	32 MB/4-cores
Vector support	AVX2
Network connection	2 × 100 Gb/s injection ports per node

System software

The ARCHER2 system uses the HPE Cray Linux Environment (CLE, based on SLES 15) as its operating system. The HPE Cray Programming Environment (CPE) provides a suite of compilers, software libraries, and tools:

- Compilers:
 - HPE Cray Compiling Environment (CCE)
 - GNU Compiler Collection (GCC)
 - AMD Optimizing Compiler Collection (AOCC)
- Parallel libraries:
 - MPI: HPE Cray MPICH2
 - HPE Cray OpenSHMEM
 - Global Arrays Toolkit
- HPE Cray scientific and numerical libraries:
 - HPE Cray LibSci: BLAS, LAPACK, ScaLAPACK
 - FFTW 3
 - NetCDF
 - HDF5
- Tools:
 - gdb4hpc parallel debugger
 - valgrind4hpc parallel memory debugging
 - STAT stack trace analysis tool
 - ATP abnormal program termination analysis tool
 - HPE Cray Performance Analysis Toolkit (CrayPAT)
 - Python
 - R

To ensure fair access to resources across all users of the service, the Slurm scheduling software is used to control access to compute resources. Configuration and use of the scheduler is described in more detail in the appropriate section of the ARCHER2 User and Best Practice Guide².

6. Service Provision

System administration

System administration for ARCHER2 is provided by the EPCC Systems Team. The team has extensive experience of systems administration of HPC systems and is well placed to provide both day-to-day operational administration as well as troubleshooting and the management of changes to the system.

User, project, and resource management tasks on ARCHER2 are conducted via a Rundeck instance. A series of tickets are defined in Rundeck to conduct various actions. All Rundeck tickets for the ARCHER2 service which carry out direct actions, including those interacting with Slurm, are intended to be:

- atomic: in each case, individual actions are created as tickets
- idempotent: tickets should be re-runnable without adverse impact or failure

“Macro” tickets are then defined which call the tickets directly interacting with ARCHER2. These tickets can call several individual “micro” tickets in sequence. Tickets are issued by the SAFE user and project management tool (described below).

In this way, most low-level user management and project management is automated on ARCHER2, including:

- Management of projects and users in LDAP.
- Management of sudo rights for access to functional accounts.
- Management of file system directory creation, removal and quota.
- Management of users and budgets within Slurm.

Service desk

The ARCHER2 service provides a service desk to prospective and current users of the Service. It is available between the hours of 0800 and 1800, Monday–Friday (excluding UK Bank Holidays). Users typically contact the service desk via email, but users can also submit a query via the SAFE.

The Service Desk is staffed by experienced members of the ARCHER2 Service team who can assess the nature of the issue and then either deal with the issue directly or assign it to an appropriate member of staff. We aim to personally acknowledge queries within 3 hours and—along with the acknowledgement of the query—we assign a service level to the query and an estimated resolution time, which is communicated to the user. Queries are designated either as SP or CSE queries and then further designated as Level 1, 2, and 3 queries, depending on the estimated complexity. Each query metric has a different Service Level Agreement which we report on a quarterly basis.

The Service Desk is the face of the ARCHER2 service to the user community and we value the personal interactions with the users. When dealing with queries, we ensure polite, timely communications whilst working to resolve the issues. Once the query has been resolved, the Service Desk asks the user for feedback on the handling of the query. To date, the feedback has been consistently high: if there is an identified issue, this is followed up with the user.

SAFE

SAFE (Service Administration from EPCC) is a bespoke web application, developed over many years by EPCC, which has the primary purpose of supporting large-scale HPC services. SAFE provides several functions, including:

- User account and research project management for ARCHER2

² Scheduler section of ARCHER2 User and Best Practice Guide: <https://docs.archer2.ac.uk/user-guide/scheduler/> (accessed on 9th December 2024).

- Management and tracking of resource usage: compute and storage resources
- Service usage reporting
- Running the ARCHER2 Service Desk and collecting feedback
- Managing applications and technical assessments for applicants for service access

SAFE has previously been used on the UK national supercomputing services: HPC(x), HECToR and ARCHER and is currently used for ARCHER2 and a range of other services hosted by EPCC and by other organisations. SAFE is developed by an EPCC team on an ongoing basis to support service improvements and changes in requirements.

User registration and account management is handled through the SAFE. This is particularly important for national HPC services like ARCHER2 as there is no pre-existing organisation to which all users belong. The SAFE acts as a self-service portal allowing users to configure and manage their accounts, and allowing project leaders and their designated representatives to view and manage their projects and the resources allocated to them. Actions generated through SAFE are automatically processed on the service itself (using Rundeck, as described above) allowing near-instantaneous changes in resource allocations, storage quotas, and user access rights.

Reporting on resource usage is available through the SAFE at all levels, enabling service-wide reporting, project- or science-consortium-level reporting and user-level reporting. The integrated nature of the SAFE allows data from many different sources to be combined when generating reports, allowing SP to analyse and understand service usage to support continual improvements throughout the service.

Environmental sustainability

Environmental sustainability is a key focus for the ARCHER2 service—both in terms of day-to-day operation and research and development activities—to understand how the environmental sustainability of ARCHER2 can continue to be improved over its lifetime and to develop improvements for future services. Key work on reducing the power draw of the ARCHER2 service, while maintaining research output, is described in a technical report: Emissions and energy efficiency on large-scale high performance computing facilities: *ARCHER2 UK national supercomputing service case study*³. The service is investigating the use of tools to enable flexible power capping on a per-node basis to further improve the flexibility of the service to reduce power draw while maintaining performance.

As well as work to optimise the power draw, the service is working to understand the emissions impact of large-scale HPC systems such as ARCHER2 and is collaborating with the wider digital infrastructure community to share experience and expertise.

7. Computational Science and Engineering

The CSE service is designed to provide a high-quality, user driven service that allows users to perform world-leading research on the ARCHER2 system and thus maximise the benefit of ARCHER2 to UK science. It is designed to ensure that the user community have the technical support, training and access to RSE effort they require to perform this world-leading scientific research.

CSE is based on a series of Functions, Activities and Processes designed within an ITIL service framework within our ISO9001-accredited Quality Management System (QMS). The key functions are:

- The CSE Service Desk underpins CSE and is the first point of contact for users; handling queries, technical assessments, and daily liaison.
- The Technical Operations function ensures users have access to a rich programming environment with supporting documentation.
- In-depth support delivers expertise, to support users to exploit the potential of ARCHER2.

³ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.05440> (accessed on 9th December 2024).

- The eCSE function delivers the eCSE programme, an independent, peer-reviewed programme of funding to improve software by research software engineering (RSE)⁴ staff embedded within the community.
- The Training function delivers the whole training programme, ensuring a high-quality innovative training programme.
- Recognising the importance of demonstrating the impact of the ARCHER2 service, the Outreach and Impact function ensures that the Service achieves maximum impact and that outreach to the wider community and public is performed.
- The Quality and Feedback function spans all our CSE activities and covers feedback, quality, improvement and data security.

The CSE Service Desk is the first point of contact for users on a day-to-day basis. It is fully integrated with the ARCHER2 Service Desk provided by the SP Provider, to ensure a coherent and integrated service for users. Service Desk shifts are staffed by experienced, technical staff with a clearly defined escalation route, should it be required.

Technical Operations provides a portfolio of activities designed to proactively ensure users have access to a rich programming environment on ARCHER2, which is tested, monitored, maintained, and continually improved. These activities include porting and enabling a range of scientific applications, tools and libraries on the ARCHER2 service; developing appropriate documentation; and developing and maintaining web pages that provide relevant, consistent and fully up-to-date information.

In-depth support activities recognise that the ARCHER2 community is scientifically, technically, and geographically diverse, and will require different modes of support at different times. We therefore offer a range of activities including queries, technical webinars and Consortium Contacts. Users can request a virtual consultancy session, where they can speak directly to a CSE technical staff member about their support requirements on ARCHER2.

The eCSE programme funds dedicated Research Software Engineering (RSE) staff embedded within their research communities to develop the UK's software base and thus enhance the benefit of ARCHER2 to UK science. Funding is allocated using an open, fair, and peer-reviewed funding programme. The service supports diversity and inclusion and promotes engagement from specific target areas, such as early career researchers, agreed with an independent panel. There is a regular series of calls for proposals, with three calls per year. The programme is underpinned by four core values: openness, independence, transparency, and not-for-profit.

The training function provides a rich, diverse programme of training that is responsive to users' evolving needs. There is a strong emphasis on improving accessibility and inclusivity of HPC training through a variety of formats and delivery routes, using best practice to make content accessible and developing policies that promote diversity and inclusion in the community. The programme has training tracks aimed specifically at researchers (who primarily use existing research software packages for their research) and RSEs/developers (who develop research software packages for their own research or for use by the wider research community). Collaborating with the community is also key to maximise the benefits of courses and the function develops training jointly with community experts whenever appropriate.

The service delivers an absorbing, innovative, and diverse programme of outreach and public engagement activities. The programme is designed to be UK-wide with events and activities available to the whole of the UK. Many of our largest outreach activities are targeted at young people, with an aim of explaining the relevance and benefit of HPC to society and of encouraging young people to consider a career in STEM. Engagement activities are aimed at the HPC community, bringing together RSEs, software developers, HPC service providers, and users to provide opportunities to build and shape the UK's HPC community. There are activities aimed at celebrating diversity in HPC and encouraging greater diversity in the HPC community.

⁴ <https://society-rse.org/about/>

The Quality and Feedback function monitors the effectiveness of the core CSE support provided. This underpins all CSE Service functions and processes. It ensures that the CSE service is delivered to the required quality and that opportunities for service improvement are identified and acted upon.

8. Hosting and accommodation

Advanced Computing Facility (ACF)

Built in the 1970s and operated by EPCC since the turn of the millennium, the Advanced Computing Facility (ACF) site has had significant investment over the years. At present, there are four computer rooms: Computer Room 1 (cr1), Computer Room 2 (cr2), Computer Room 3 (cr3) and Computer Room 4 (cr4). Each computer room hosts specific equipment and is supported by associated plant rooms, which provide dedicated power and cooling infrastructure to support systems hosted in corresponding room. We have several pieces of equipment and racks at our site which are “traditionally” air cooled, but most of our equipment and speciality HPC systems are water cooled. ARCHER2 is a direct-liquid-cooled system, hosted in cr3 and supported by the dedicated Plant Room C (prC).

The ACF operates a 200 Gbit/s Data Centre Network to support systems hosted on-site and connects to JANET (the UK’s Joint Academic NETWORK) at 100 Gbit/s for user access and data transfer.

The available power capacity was upgraded from 8 MW to 38 MW in 2023 as part of the longer-term strategy for the ACF. ARCHER2 currently typically consumes 2.5–2.8 MW, with all electricity used at the ACF being supplied with a Renewable Energy Guarantees of Origin (REGO) certificate to assure that power has originated from a renewable supply.

We work to utilise free cooling (the cooling of systems solely using outside air via water pumped to fans on the roof) as far as possible throughout the year and our systems will automatically use this whenever outside air temperatures are sufficiently low. Typically, we can make use of 100% free-cooling where the outside air temperature is 12 degrees Celsius or less – much of the year in Scotland. When ambient temperatures are too high to allow 100% free cooling then, the chiller units in prC provide additional cooling capacity.

Site biodiversity

The UK is ranked as the lowest G7 nation for biodiversity intactness and has seen a 19% decline in species abundance since 1970. The University of Edinburgh is a signatory of the Nature Positive Universities Alliance and EPCC is committed to understanding the impact our service activities have on biodiversity. We are investigating the impact on biodiversity from the production of ARCHER2 and looking at ways to reduce the impact during decommissioning through effective waste management.

We also aim to protect and enhance biodiversity on the ACF site. We have worked to protect the existing biodiversity, with the computer rooms being located around a traditional, central, tree roundel and an area of wetland left untouched for wildlife. We have also enhanced conditions for biodiversity to thrive—planting diverse native hedgerows, creating wildlife meadows for pollinators, and creating wildlife corridors through fencing. Felled wood has been used to provide habitats for insects on site.

9. Professional standards and accreditation

To ensure that best practice is applied, and the success of improvement activities is monitored, EPCC has invested the time and staff effort to obtain and maintain a series of world-wide, recognised ISO certifications. For each of these certifications and management systems, EPCC carries out an annual program of internal audits, ensuring that the management systems are delivering the expected benefits to ARCHER2 users and to UKRI. Annually, there is an external audit by an accredited external auditor, to ensure that EPCC is complying with the requirements of the relevant standards.

- ISO 9001 is a globally recognised quality management standard, that can be applied to almost any type of business providing services or manufacturing products. EPCC uses it to ensure it delivers great service to the ARCHER2 users and meets and exceeds the terms of the ARCHER2

contracts and agreements. User feedback is collected, analysed and acted upon to drive continual improvements.

- ISO 27001 is a globally recognised risk-based information security standard. EPCC has recently achieved re-certification to the latest version, ISO 27001:2022, which has a much greater emphasis on the prevention of cyber security incidents than the previous version. The standard covers everything from the employment of trusted staff and information security in supply chains through to the technical security controls and measures needed to meet requirements for accessibility, confidentiality, integrity and availability.
- ISO 22301 is a globally recognised business continuity and disaster recovery standard. EPCC has taken a risk-based approach to identifying the core components of the services it runs and uses the impact each has on the ARCHER2 service and its users to set priorities. Business continuity is supported by the documentation of processes, the training of staff, and the removal of single points of failure. Disaster recovery is monitored by the regular testing of different aspects of services and then making improvements based on the tests.

In addition to the professional certifications described above, EPCC also employs industry best practice for operating digital research infrastructure. We use the ITIL framework to help us deliver high-quality services. ITIL is an internationally recognised framework for delivering high-quality IT services in the digital era. The current version, ITIL4, addresses a new way of managing services, called *high-velocity IT*, which focuses on creating value streams, enabling agility, and promoting iterative improvement. Using ITIL4 methodologies has allowed us to develop an effective and efficient ARCHER2 service (a complex, multi-layered operation involving multiple partners and suppliers) and enables us to continually evolve ARCHER2 to track emerging trends in computational science. Since the early days of the ARCHER2 service, back in 2018, EPCC has employed ITIL to support both its CSE and SP operations. Staff are encouraged to pursue ITIL certification and our approach to managing ARCHER2 and its supporting services is guided by ITIL4.

The presence of ITIL4 is mostly transparent to end users and stakeholders, though everyone benefits from its use through, for example, the ARCHER2 Service Desk, incident response, service development and delivery, and stakeholder engagement. As an internationally recognised approach, ITIL4 creates a common language for IT service delivery: users who have been exposed to ITIL will recognise and understand many of the elements of the ARCHER2 service and IT professionals with ITIL experience can more easily engage with or support ARCHER2 service delivery.

10. Further information

More detailed information about the service can be found on the ARCHER2 website (<https://www.archer2.ac.uk>) and in the extensive online documentation (<https://docs.archer2.ac.uk>).